

Architecture for the SCALIBUR Cloud Platform including planned quality measures

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The exponential growth and widespread availability of Internet, brought to the birth of new and modern software paradigms. The vast majority of software vendors abandoned the so called on premises software distribution, in which the software was delivered to the customer on a physical memory support device, to embrace the Software as a Service (SaaS) distribution model. This model foresees the availability of the software through the Internet connection, and it is typically hosted by a hosting service provider. The SaaS paradigm caused a deep change on the methodologies and technique used to build the software, and opened to new possibilities and new markets.

The SCALIBUR Cloud Platform follows this new modern paradigm and embrace the new potentialities of this new business methodology. The platform will be accessible from any device over the Internet without requiring to install any proprietary software as it was in the past.

Evolving in this direction, the SCALIBUR Cloud Platform has been designed to fulfill the new requirements born from the new implementation methodology to ensure a high-quality level of the software. A layered structure has been defined to be scalable and adaptable to the different needs that can be rose throughout the execution of the project.

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